

Encryption Techniques for Blockchain-Based IoT Networks: A Systematic Literature Review

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Author's note

This paper presents the author's Master of Information Technology thesis, originally completed in 2019 at Charles Sturt University. It is being made available here for reference and broader accessibility. The text has been lightly revised for grammatical clarity and readability; no changes have been made to the original research content, methodology, findings, or conclusions.

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Abstract

The Internet of Things is the future of the Internet. However, the computational capacity and size of these devices make it extremely difficult to preserve privacy. As most algorithms are highly energy-consuming, and these devices sometimes have limited data capacity, it is essential to develop techniques that will serve as the backbone of internet security in the future. With the aim of connecting everything to the Internet, it will be essential to implement security solutions to address privacy, integrity, and other security issues. This paper aims to identify the best possible solutions to address the constraints inherent in IoT devices within the IoT network. This paper focuses on the implementation of encryption techniques when blockchain technology is used for IoT networks. The review covers algorithms such as greedy scheduling, public and private encryption, and symmetric and asymmetric key algorithms, drawing on specific papers that discuss their own proposed schemes.

By reading this paper, readers will be able to understand the options that can be implemented in IoT devices without significantly affecting their energy consumption. Readers will also understand how these small devices can be secured using various methods. The reader will find information on the classification groups, future research, and validation criteria of the 30 core literature reviews examined in depth, along with the security, privacy, integrity, and computational capacity of IoT devices.

Keywords: Encryption, Blockchain, Internet of Things, Security, Privacy, Cryptography

1. Introduction

The Internet is going through a very rapid growth phase, and there are many new technologies evolving along with its growth. The Internet of Things is one of those technologies that has made it through to the global market in this field. With every new technology comes a new challenge. With the aim of being implemented in everything, it has brought various challenges that have to be addressed with utmost priority if it is to be considered for such a large-scale integration into the lifestyle of everyone in this world (Moin et al., 2019). The focus is to achieve high security without compromising the computational cost of the small IoT devices, so that their energy will not be drained more than it should. Also, maintaining high security will let it be implemented in any form and any sector, like finance, medicine, and public security. This is achieved by using lightweight cryptographic mechanisms, which will help preserve the energy of the devices. Additionally, when the device itself cannot be encrypted, the nodes and blocks to which it is connected can be secured as well (Banerjee et al., 2019).

Blockchain is another new technology that has been introduced recently after the emergence of the cryptocurrency superpower Bitcoin. Blockchain is a technique that allows data sharing between two non-trusting blocks. This was proved to be secure once Bitcoin successfully implemented it in its technology. Blockchain is a chain of blocks where every block is responsible for carrying out a certain task. It is an indexing system where the integrity of data is maintained (Altulyan et al., 2019). But blockchain alone is not enough to secure the IoT network, as the most fragile part of the IoT network is the devices, which are far more constrained than other devices in the computing world. Devices like LED bulbs, water level sensors, and many other very small devices will not be able to do more than pass data in bits. Also, these devices have very limited battery power, so this case must be considered as well. It might not be a good idea to implement just the cryptographic mechanisms, but according to the situation, implementing security at the blocks can be the most feasible option to consider (Agyekum et al., 2019).

The major objective of this research paper is to address the issues with IoT devices, the issues that the devices will face, and the adverse effects they can lead to, which can be in terms of financial loss or any other sort of loss. Furthermore, we will point out the best possible options and some of those options that would not be feasible for IoT network implementation. This paper will discuss topics like the HEVC encryption scheme, FogBus scheme, searchable encryption scheme, asymmetric encryption scheme, anonymisation, mixing, publish/subscribe model, cellular automata-based encryption, along with bit and block encryption. We will also discuss the use of private and public encryption in blockchain technology in the IoT network.

We have reviewed the role encryption plays in securing the blockchain-based IoT network. We have also discussed how encryption sometimes cannot be implemented on the devices, no matter how low the computational code we run on the device. We will be viewing 3 publications which have discussed how multimedia IoT devices can be secured. We will be listing 2 publications which will show how a searchable keyword asymmetric scheme can be used to secure the communication between devices. Additionally, we will be discussing 13 papers, which will include

the equations that have been proposed in every publication that has been researched, and review the best possible option to implement on the IoT system and IoT devices.

Moving forward to the various encryption methods available, our paper will choose the best option, which will not affect the computational cost and which will cost less to implement in an actual environment when billions of devices are to be considered. Because of this reason, we will include 2 publications specific to firmware update and software update on the IoT platform, which will also provide batch verification. This will lead to the successful deployment of the devices and make sure that the system is updated whenever required, as with every new second comes every new vulnerability.

2. Literature Review

A lot more research that has been done before has focused on how AES, DES and SHA series can be implemented on IoT network and devices. We will particularly discuss other papers that have focused on new approaches towards secure IoT network schemes, along with their overall working, advantages, and disadvantages.

Securing a system is not just about securing its applications; its hardware can be secured as well, if required. Banerjee et al. (2019) introduced this same technique in their paper, "Hardware implementation for security using the datagram transport layer security protocol." This paper used a 65-nm CMOS chip, which is low power. Also, a low power RISC-V processor is used. This technology focuses more on hardware implementation, which leads to secure IoT devices. Additionally, cryptographic accelerators have been used to boost the cryptographic power for the IoT devices.

Zhao et al. (2019) proposed a software update technique for IoT devices, which would also provide proof of delivery of the IoT device update. It is lower in ECDSA and ElGamal method. Also, DAPS time is decreased as well. Hu et al. (2019) proposed a firmware update technique that would ensure the firmware can be upgraded without any negative effect from malware and autonomous effect. Batch verification is used so that the integrity of the update is maintained, ensuring that if batch verification is unsuccessful, further updates can be done until it is satisfied.

Li et al. (2019) put forward a blockchain-based searchable symmetric encryption scheme that uses a private key and successfully shows its implementation. Encryption is enabled while searching as well, which leads to a secure blockchain-based IoT network — a new concept introduced in the publications researched. It is related to the time and generation of the token, which also includes searching time. A linear increment was seen, providing evidence for this. Wang et al. (2019) has also proposed an attribute-based encryption and keyword searchable scheme. It provides an equality test, which allows secure establishment of security among two blocks.

However, Yang et al. (2019) proposed the use of a named data networking environment so that the identifier is not exposed. It states that the SHA series is not recommended because of its high computational cost. Because of this reason, an NDN environment is proposed, also because of its attribute-based encryption. This paper used personal attributes instead of ID, because of which the data is not compromised. This is seen as one of the prominent solutions to secure IoT network integration.

Lv et al. (2019) then proposed a Publish/Subscribe model, which used a publish and subscribe model. This model, however, is named as such, but there are other models that have used the same technique. But, unlike other techniques, this technique, when implemented, results in a decrement in the length of the message, while speed and security are both improved. Additionally, according to Roy et al. (2019), a lightweight cellular automata-based cipher would also be useful in providing security. Frequency, cumulative sums, non-overlapping template, and universal approximate entropy were all a success.

Quality of Service is an important aspect in any service. Roy et al. (2019) proposed a technique where an MQTT broker is used. This helps in preventing a Man in the Middle attack. This is especially important, as this paper also provides a solution to the congestion control mechanism. Because of the use of blockchain technology, risk recovery is also successful due to the indexing system of the blockchain network. Similarly, Altulyan et al. (2019) has also provided a similar technique, but without the use of an MQTT broker. This helps in providing data integrity in people-centric smart cities. It uses secret sharing and a fog computing layer. This also proves to be important in preventing Man in the Middle attacks. However, this paper provides more information on the security level, with discussion on data filtering and extracting. Zhu et al. (2019) has provided information on ZSS signature, which also helps in data integrity verification. Along with this paper, Al-Zubi and Abu-Shareha (2018) proposed signcryption based on El Gamal and Schnorr, which is very efficient in providing security to multiple aspects of an IoT network. It provides security and reduces computational cost. It ensures confidentiality, integrity, unforgeability, and verifiability. The best part about this topic is that keys of up to 160 bits are generated, but the drawback is that it would not be possible to run directly on the IoT devices.

However, Xu et al. (2019) brought up a technique that can be used to prevent the keyword guessing attack, but in comparison to Li et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2019), this technique is more focused on just the keyword guessing attack. However, with the other two techniques, it has also provided an encryption scheme that secures the keywords. But the technique proposed by Xu et al. (2019) is time-controlled, which is actually a very good option because it provides a very lightweight solution; however, due to its lower computational cost, it also becomes a significant vulnerability to attacks.

As discussed earlier, Sun et al. (2019) proposed lightweight geometric routing, which is very useful in providing security and helps provide the shortest and safest possible path. Greedy embedding

helps provide a secure connection from the darknet as well. This paper has also discussed prefix embedding and PIE, which make up the geometric routing proposed in this paper.

Another scheme that discusses inner workings and provides a solution with its own proposal deals with FogBus. FogBus, as proposed by Tuli et al. (2019), provides an excellent solution for saving computational cost and also provides security with high privacy. This can lead to a successful implementation of the IoT network.

All these techniques can be used to provide a higher quality of service, along with security, and in this paper we will compare the attributes used, equations, size, and success factors of the technologies that have been used. This will lead us to finding solutions and provide a review of some of the systems that have been proposed but could not be implemented. In this paper, we will be focusing particularly on the NDN environment for security and providing high quality of service.

Figure 1 NDN environment detailed diagram

3. System Components

In system components, we have separated our factor classes into three sections: Data, Processing, and Output. In Data, we include ciphertext, plaintext, and encryption method. This is essential because these are the actual data entries that we will be working with. The plaintext can be an input from the sensors or any other IoT devices, whereas ciphertext is its respective encrypted message.

As encryption is done using a dedicated code that helps hide the data in simple meaning, it is considered the third data entry.

Then, in Processing, we use algorithm, as it is the algorithm that is used to process the data. Without any algorithm, data could not be processed. An algorithm should not just be a program but can be implemented in any hardware-based system as well. Furthermore, we have used security, privacy, Quality of Service, integrity, and resource management as our Output. This is all essential because even if IoT devices are constrained, they cannot be implemented without these factors. Here, the data is stored in bit, byte, KB, MB, but we are not discussing GB, as the data we will deal with will be relatively small.

The basic working diagram of the system can be seen below:

Figure 2 Basic Working Diagram for the technology mentioned

For this purpose, we have developed an attribute table that provides these details, including the factor/class, main attributes, and mutual instances. The first factor used is data, which is further subdivided into four parts: plaintext, ciphertext, encryption method, and prediction technique. This is then processed using a certain encryption algorithm, which is the second factor. Finally, output is used, which includes resource management. Output is the third factor.

Table 1 Factor Table: Data, processing and output

Factor/Class	Main attributes	Mutual Instances
Data	Size of data	Bit, byte, kb, mb
Plaintext	Initial input without encryption	Input data (Confirm)
Ciphertext	Plaintext computed with encryption	During processing, before entering key, cryptocurrencies
Encryption method	Fixed methods, changing random values	
Prediction technique	Algorithm	Searchable symmetric encryption, edge and fog computing, cryptocurrencies, anonymization electronic patient record, financial transactions, vehicular networks, energy systems, KeyGen
Processing	Encryption	RSA, Fogbus, DES Family, SHA Family, AES
Algorithm	Processor	FOGBUS, AES, DES
Output	Security (Encrypted)	Symmetric encryption, FogBus,
Resource Management	Integrity, Privacy, QoS	FogBus, Privacy preserving mechanism, privacy focused altcoin, tracing anonymous transactions, cryptography, mixing, differential privacy, smart contract

3.1 Data

Data is the most important part of the flow in the network. Without data being generated, there is no use for any algorithm. Thus, plaintext becomes the most important part of the data flow, as it is what is to be encrypted in this process. Then, a prediction technique, such as a keyword searchable algorithm, is utilised, which is then encrypted using an encryption method. The encryption method processes the data using a certain hashing algorithm, which causes the data to be encrypted. Then, the ciphertext is generated, which is the actual data that is transmitted in the network.

3.2 Processing

Processing is another factor. In this factor, algorithm is included, where an algorithm is used in both cases — when the plaintext is encrypted or the ciphertext is decrypted. The prediction technique is utilised using encryption as well. Also, encrypted data is processed during the processing stage.

3.3 Output

The final factor is the output. When the data is processed using a certain encryption method, the output is better management of the resources — in this case, data, finance, and other stakes that are dependent on it. Security, integrity, and storage become a vital task in this as well.

The major reason for using plaintext, ciphertext, prediction technique, and encryption data as the data technique is that without this, everything flowing in the network is compromised. The whole technique behind saving the data is to prevent malicious activity from occurring on the network.

4. Classification Table

The classification table provided below illustrates the journal papers that have been reviewed in relation to the criteria and system components, and their further sub-components, which are encryption used, data, processing, and output.

Table 2 System Component Table

Ref	Encryption used	Data		Processing		Output		
		Plaintext	Ciphertext	Encryption method	Algorithm	Resource Management	Security	Integrity, Privacy, QoS
(Li, Tian, Zhang & He, 2019)	Searchable encrypted scheme	As a document	Use of private key using a keyword for the document	Searchable encryption scheme	Use of in-script, withdraw, pay	Management of bitcoin related technique	Linear growth shown using chart	Validated using char with linear growth
(Tuli, Mahmud, Tuli & Buyya, 2019)	N/S	Basic	Encrypted with no formula provided	FogBus	FogBus, Stack4Things, Cloudlet based Paas and InDie Fog	FogBus	FogBus	FogBus
(Li, Susilo, Yang, Yu, Du, Liu & Guizani, 2019)	Tate pairing as an asymmetric bilinear map	Input account	Ciphertext C	Tag, R	ElGamal encryption	N/S	N/S	KeyGen: 7.797 ms Spend: 3.12 ms Trace: 6.331 ms Transaction Size: 3 KB
(Hassan, Rehmani & Chen, 2019)	Anonymization and Mixing	Basic Plaintext	Use of mixing of bits	Anonymization and mixing	Encryption, mixing, private contract, anonymization, differential privacy	Private Contract	Encryption, Mixing	Differential privacy, anonymization, mixing, private contract
(Lv, Wang, Zhu, Deng & Gu, 2019)	Publish/Subscribe model	Publish 0.519 ms	Subscribe – 15.144 ms	Match – 4.165 ms	Receuve – 1.796 ms	NA	NA	NA
(Roy, Rawat and Karjee, 2019)	Lightweight cellular automata-based encryption	Alrorthm 1,2,3 8 LENGTH CA RULE	Alrorthm 1,2,3	Alrorthm 1,2,3	Rule 102,150,51,153,195,75,90	Cumulative sums, runs, longest runs of ones, rank, FFT, non-overlapping template, universal approximate entropy, serial, linear complexity	Included along with resource management RVLIST512, LOST OF GCA RULE VECTORS HAVING CYCLE LENGTH EQUALS TO 8	Included along with resource management

(Feng et al., 2019)	Non interactive zero knowledge proof	NS	NS	Mixing services, ring signature, non-interactive zero-knowledge proof	NS	Completeness, soundness, zero knowledge	NS	NS
(Guo, Hua, Zhang & Wang, 2019)	Block encryption algorithm	Applied on device not having capacity to process AES and DES, HXMD is operated	NA	SAFER K-64, K-128, SK-64, SK-128, SK-40, =, ++	NA	Yes	Yes	Yes
(Yan et al., 2019)	Function based access control	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Lower access time
(Banerjee et al., 2019)	DTLS cryptographic engine, hardware implementation	C'	Q, A, B, DM SHA-156	Invoked AES-GCM 128-bit block of data (Every)	Retrieve (Registered trademark sign)	65 nm CMOS	Energy saved 10 times	Handshake provides it
(Unde & P., 2019)	CSSM, CSSM-EM	NA	NS	Chosen Plaintext attack, SRM, Artificial noise, SRM, Quantized CS	NA	Analysis And simulation	NS	NS
(Kim, Hu, Sarkar & Jha, 2019)	Use of commissioner, policy group, centralized server, devices.	Compressive sensing based lightweight encryption scheme	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
(Li et al., 2019)	Ciphertext only fault analysis	64-bit plaintext	AES	AES	AES	Provided	Provided	NA – 1.41 to 2.81 seconds is enough to break it
(Moin et al., 2019)	JUST A DISCUSSION	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS
(Zhang et al., 2019)	Semi-outsourcing privacy preserving scheme	Setup, Key initialize, authentication	AES USED	Public key cryptography	Decrypt	Provided	Provided	Provided
(Yang, Cha and Song, 2019)	Attribute based encryption	Named Data networking management	NA	NA	NDN environment	Secure identifier management	NA	NA
(Zhao, Liu, Tian, Yu & Du, 2019)	NA	NA	NA	NA	20 attributes to validate output	NA	NA	Validated using Lemma 1,2,3,4 and 5
(Hu, Yeh, Liao & Yang, 2019)	Bilinearity, non-degeneracy, symmetric	Full node, client node, storing node, manufacturer node	NA	Batch verification	NA	NA	NA	Provided using batch verification
(Sun et al., 2019)	Lightweight geometric routing	Algorithm, 1, 2, 3	RS, DS (Confuse mechanism)	Use of F2F which is friend to friend	Greedy embedding	YES	YES	YES
(Makhdoom, Abolhasan, Abbas & Ni, 2019)	TX Validation Rules	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	Resilient against Sybil attack, consensus finality, avoiding forks
(Wang, Yao, Chen & Zhang, 2019)	Attribute based encryption Keyword searchable	Compare with one above	Inverted Index	NS	Use of Intel core i5-3740 CPU@3.20 GHz. RAM IS 4GB Development kit version 1.7.5, JPBC 2.0.0 and My Eclipse 10	NS	NS	NS

(Xu et al., 2019)	Time controlled public key encryption scheme	Keyword	Keywords guessing, Time control	Time controlled public key encryption scheme	Delegable conjunctive keyword search	Yes	Yes	It prevents guessing attack
(Al-Zubi & Abu-Shareha, 2018)	Signcryption El-Gamal Schnorr Public key encryption	Not to just plan data but to blocks of data				Reduce computational cost,	Prove confidentiality, prove integrity	Prove unforgeability and prove verifiability
(Zhu et al., 2019)	Data integrity verification scheme	Length not provided	Private key used to encrypt and make it a ciphertext	100 data blocks used for the test		Slight increment for ZSS and steep increment for BLS		
(Rao & Prema, 2019)	BLAKE2b hashing algorithm Modified Elliptic curve digital signature					0.7%-1.91% improvement in the signature generation time 7.67-9.13% improvement in signature verification time	No Man in middle	No DDoS, pre image resistance provided, collision resistance
(Altulyan, Yao, Kanhere, Wang & Huang, 2019)	Layerwise protection SIGN SHARED APPROACH	NA	NA	Secret sharing layer, fog computing layer, blockchain layer	Checksum and cyclic redundancy check	NA	NA	Provided
(Jan et al., 2019)	Payload based mutual authentication scheme	All data sent	Authentication between users using mutual authentication scheme	AES-128-bit key length with constraint application protocol	AES-128-bit key length with constraint application protocol	Handshake lets this happen, nodes prevention used as well	Yes	Lightweight features of CoAP allows this to happen
(Roy et al., 2019)	MQTT Broker	Algorithm 1, 2, 3 and 4 used for input data	NA	NA	NA	Yes	NA	NA
(Thiyagarajan et al., 2019)	HEVC encryption scheme	Multimedia	NS	NS	NS	Provided according to the statistics displayed	NA	NS
(Agyekum et al., 2019)	Data sharing module used using a proxy	Use of vectors to convert then	Bilinear maps used	Inner-product encryption scheme	Use of ciphertexts and private keys	Provided	But high end to end data processing time	NA

5. Validation and Evaluation

Table 3 Validation and Evaluation: Elaborative articles

S. N	Reference	Clinical Procedure	Component Validated and Transmitted	Study criteria	Specific Tools	Output	Results
1	(Lv, Wang, Zhu, Deng & Gu, 2019)	Publish/subscribe model is used	Use of publish subscribe model allowed to share file or data between the users having the required key	$M = \text{dec}_y(C_s)$	Publish, subscribe and blockchain used simultaneously	Efficiency increase with increase in length of the message. Speed and security both provided	Better performance in terms of time
2	(Roy, Rawat and Karjee, 2019)	Lightweight cellular automata-based encryption technique is used	Lightweight Cellular automata-based cipher, programmable cellular automata as per the requirement	CA Rule - No. = $\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S_k t^k$	Cellular automata	Successful in providing security with the results shown with pass rate on all the criteria researched in	All evaluation criteria passed
3	(Guo, Hua, Zhang & Wang, 2019)	Secure and fast encryption scheme (SAFER) used	SAFER-Fermat block encryption used even on IoT devices	(S ₁ , S ₂) which are two nonlinear transforms are applied on X. This means: (S ₁ (X ¹), S ₂ (X ²), S ₂ (X ³), S ₁ (X ⁴), ..., S ₁ (X ¹³), S ₁ (X ¹⁴), S ₁ (X ¹⁵), S ₁ (X ¹⁶))	SAFER K-64 SAFER K-128 SAFER SK-64 SAFER SK-128 SAFER SK-40 SAFER= SAFER++	Success rate is a success as provided at the results.	Frequency balance test, plaintext and ciphertext independence test and diffusion test is all successful.
4	(Yan et al., 2019)	IoT-FBAC (Function based access control) is used	Use of FBAC, Encryption key and ID Secret key is used as well to validate.	$A = g^{s-ID} X^s$ $B = Y^s$ $D = e(g, g)^s \cdot M$	IoT-FBAC and FACT is compared which helps us to know that it performs better than FACT	All the test in comparison to FACT is provided	Data security is provided in FBAC, but it is not provided in FACT. Space saving is provided in FBAC, but it is not provided in FACT
5	(Banerjee et al., 2019)	Hardware implementation with implementation of the datagram transport layer security (DTLS) protocol	Security is provided by implementing it in hardware level	$E_{\text{total}} = E_{\text{handshake}} + (N \times (t_{\text{session}}/t_{\text{appdata}}) \times E_{\text{appdata}})$	DTLS, cryptographic accelerators, code size, data memory, low power RISC-V processor, test chip and 65-nm CMOS was used	SHA AND AES-GCM was used which has been trusted in security field for years.	Cache missed, data and security all passed
6	(Unde & P., 2019)	Compressive sensing based lightweight encryption	Upgrade on Compressive sensing-based energy efficient	$\hat{\phi}_j = \arg \min_{\phi_j \in \{\pm 1\}} (y_j - \phi_j \mathbf{x})$	CSSM, CSSM-EM, CPA, Artificial noise, SRM,	The data changed and all the values were different	No information leakage

		scheme was used	encryption scheme with use of an SRM		quantized CS was compared and used	than it was at first	
7	(Kim, Hu, Sarkar & Jha, 2019)	Identity based broadcast encryption has been used. It is a management framework of industry consortium THREAD	Provides detailed report and performance criteria by outperforming the existing schemes	Uses IBBE by taking advantage of IBE and BE and provides three necessary features $CO_T \leftarrow l \cdot \sum_{i=1}^p (P_{DTLS} + P_{key} + P_{PD}) \cdot h \cdot t_i \cdot c_i$	IBBE, IBE, BE, SIBBE, THREAD has been discussed	Provided the output and was better in all aspect compared to other three frameworks	Higher performance in comparison with other three frameworks provided
8	(Li et al., 2019)	Fault analysis on the ciphertext for LED framework	This provides output on how LED framework can be compromised and see the fault analysis	$GF = \sum_{m=0}^{M-1} \frac{(O_m - E_m)^2}{E_m}$	Fault injection target, fault, recovering the key, deducing the key	Got the key in timeframe of 1.41 to 2.81 seconds.	LED framework was compromised
9	(Yang, Cha and Song, 2019)	Use of named data networking environment to not expose the identifier	This helps in not exposing the identifier with split management technique	Explains different identifiers and named data network scheme. It helps to show how blockchain functions and what happens when communication is to be done between two nodes.	SHA256 is said to be not recommended. NDN environment, attribute-based encryption	Personal attribute is used instead of the ID which helps in not compromising the data.	This helps us get the idea on how NDN can probably help in securing IoT networks that are based on blockchain without compromising the ID.

5.1 On Updates

Table 4 Validation and Evaluation: On Updates

S . N	Referenc e	Clinical Procedure	Component Validated and Transmitted	Study criteria	Specific Tools	Output	Results
1	(Zhao, Liu, Tian, Yu & Du, 2019)	Software updates with proof of delivery provided for internet of things preserving privacy	This helps us in providing the upgrades required for the system by preserving the privacy as well	IoT devices Denoted as a set of I in relation to gateway.	For security this is used, $Z = \frac{e(\sigma_2, g)}{e(\sigma_0, u_0 \prod_{j=1}^l u_j^{m_j}) e(\sigma_1, v_0 \prod_{k \in [n]} V_k^{c_k})}$	It is lower in ECDSA and ElGamal .	DAPS times: 0.007 s setup, 0.013 seconds KGen, 0.015 seconds Sign/Enc , 0.031s Ver/Dec, Ext 0.061 seconds
2	(Hu, Yeh, Liao & Yang, 2019)	Firmware update can be processed with used of autonomou	Use of batch verification making sure that the integrity is	ystem Model Blockchain Full Node Client Node	Firmware updating smart contract using $\sigma_M = v \cdot \text{PrK}_1 + w \cdot \text{PrK}_2$ For batch verification $= e(v \cdot \text{SID}_1, \text{PK}_{CA1}) \cdot e(w \cdot H_1(\text{SID}_1 \text{SID}_2), \text{PK}_{CA2})$	Overhead is less than 50	This is 5 times less than others

		s and malware proof blockchain based firmware update	maintained during this process	Storing Node Manufacturer Node			
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5.2 On keyword searchable attributes

Table 5 Validation and Evaluation: On keyword searchable attributes

S. N	Reference	Clinical Procedure	Component Validated and Transmitted	Study criteria	Specific Tools	Output	Results
1	(Li, Tian, Zhang & He, 2019)	Blockchain based searchable symmetric encryption scheme is used	Use of private key shown and properly implemented	This is used for bitcoin $T_w = \delta \cdot \text{Enck}(k_{31}, t_w \parallel k_w \parallel H(k_{31}))$ $t_{wi}, e_{wi}, \text{Mac}_{wi}$ is kept into I which is of length $m - (2k + \lambda)$	Private Key, encryption scheme related to time and generation of token including searching time	Linear increment success value increased from 2500 to 8000 after the use of this scheme and remains same.	Performance did not decrease even when the token numbers is increased from 1 to 5. Multiple keywords is introduced as well
2	(Wang, Yao, Chen & Zhang, 2019)	Attribute based encryption is used. It also has keyword searchable technique that has been implemented	This checks by comparing equality among two data that has to be converted. For this original data is not compromised.	Equation not provided. Referring to diagram and paper done.	Plaintext Ciphertext Inverted Index Equality test IoT devices	This mechanism has more attribute used. This is not an advantage when compared to the journal above where same experiment is done.	But good security is provided

5.3 New proposed system

Table 6 Validation and Evaluation: New proposed system

S. N	Reference	Clinical Procedure	Component Validated and Transmitted	Study criteria	Specific Tools	Output	Results
1	(Roy, Rawat & Karjee, 2019)	Lightweight Cellular Automata based Cipher is used	Encryption Decryption Frequency Block frequency Cumulative sums Runs Non-Overlapping template Entropy Serial Linear Complexity	CA Rule – No. = $\sum_{k=0}^{n-1} S_k t^k$	Encryption was carried out in the perception layer. Sensors are deployed here. Then decryption is done at the network layer. This is where the gateway devices are placed	The output here is either it passes or fails	Passes all the test
2	(Guo, Hua, Zhang & Wang, 2019)	Secure and fast encryption routine (SAFER) series Fermat block encryption algorithm is used	HMDX is operated for the generation of sub keys	$S_p = h \times 2^7 + I \times 2^4 + j$ $d_i = \text{HW}(C + C_i), 0 \leq I \leq n-1$	SAFER	Mentioned that if a very high computing capacity containing computer is used then it can penetrate this system but	Diffusion process The termination flag is 1 bit, 3 bits is the encryption round in processes

						doing so gives ample time.	
3	(Tuli, Mahmud, Tuli & Buyya, 2019)	FogBus is the technique that they have proposed and is used in this paper. It is a lightweight framework which works with blockchain	With the use of blockchain over other technologies, it was seen that blockchain provides a very high growth in performance of the network.	Single network of Wireless LAN is used Devices like Raspberry Pi, Gateway Android devices is used	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Broker Service • Repository Service • Computing Service • Network Structure • Service Latency • Encryption methods 	CPU Load, System initiation time, RAM load, Data retrieving time, Quality of Service is improved when FogBus is used.	Improved performance with the use of FogBus can be seen

When Li et al. (2019) used keyword searchable attributes, the linear increment success value increased from 2500 to 8000 when the scheme they proposed was used. However, when Wang et al. (2019) used their system, the time taken was less than that of the other paper researched, which made the security stronger, but it became highly ineffective in time-sensitive domains.

6. Discussion

In our discussion, we will be focusing on some aspects of the kind of encryption techniques that have been used. Also, we will not just discuss software encryption but will include papers where hardware encryption is used. For the hardware encryption, we will just be reporting on the performance but will not compare it with any other paper. Only one hardware paper will be used in the discussion, which is why we will not be including it for comparison. We will then compare papers on updates and their encryption, for the case where, if any system fails or needs an update, it can be done while also being secured at the same time. After this, we will focus on the encryption algorithms used in blockchain technology, specifically the computational cost, energy requirements, area of security, and compatibility with constrained devices. We will also focus on the encryption of the blockchain network as a whole. Blockchain evolved because of its acceptance by Bitcoin, which was equally secure and performed very well because of the approach it took for Bitcoin technology (Li et al., 2019).

6.1 Software and Firmware updates

Software updates are one of the most vital parts of any system's components. In this emerging world of technology, vulnerabilities arise every now and then, and because of that, software updates are equally important. Zhao et al. (2019) proposed a software update policy for blockchain systems, which would also have proof of delivery. Proof of delivery guarantees the delivery of the update to the remote IoT devices. Here, the relation to the gateway has been mentioned, and because of that, every relation relates to gateways for devices, ensuring that the update is done and guaranteed as well. For the process of securing the update, a publish-subscribe model was used. In this process, the time required was very low. In this paper, it has not been mentioned what can be done if the update is not possible at all, or whether any other method can be proposed.

Also, Hu et al. (2019) proposed a batch verification process as well, where firmware updates are considered. When compared with other systems, this process was completed in five times less

time. This process helps in verifying the integrity and ensures that the entire system is malware-proof. On the other hand, a dedicated encryption method has not been discussed, which would have secured the IoT devices, and the security implemented on the devices themselves has not been mentioned. Also, in the case of a higher space requirement for updates, it has not been mentioned what else can be done. But more than that, both techniques provide a unique, encrypted, secure update system for IoT devices using blockchain technology in an IoT network.

6.2 Keyword Searchable Attributes

Keyword searchable attributes are another key aspect of encrypted systems. Li et al. (2019) clearly mentioned a searchable symmetric encryption scheme where they used a private key, and it was implemented as well. They also mentioned that it was used for Bitcoin and that Bitcoin is equally secure. Furthermore, this technique used a time-related scheme, where there is a certain time for any task to be carried out. Here, the use of multiple keywords is supported as well. Generation of the token is another vital part in terms of encryption. In the case of very constrained devices, their tokens can be encrypted, and the details within them can be encrypted at the same time. If this is done, then the system would be highly secure and highly beneficial. Additionally, Wang et al. (2019) mentioned another aspect of the keyword searchable technique. Here, they encrypt the data at both ends and then check the equality of the encrypted data. With this technique, the identity of the source is not compromised either. Inverted index is also used. In this paper, the secret key generation process is shown, which also makes it more vulnerable, and it is also an easier process. This paper's output shows a contradicting view, where whenever an additional task is provided, the time is increased significantly, which is not beneficial when it comes to energy-limited devices. Because of this reason, there should be a technique like the earlier one used, where the computational cost is less, but the security is equally maintained.

6.3 Encryption based proposed schema

Additionally, some papers have brought up their own unique ways of providing security using encryption in blockchain-based IoT networks. Roy et al. (2019) proposed a lightweight cellular automata-based cipher which, just by its name, we can tell is intended for IoT systems. This system included a very high number of components that were validated and checked. They checked whether their proposal would pass in terms of encryption, decryption, frequency, block frequency, cumulative sums, runs, longest run of ones, rank, FFT, non-overlapping template, universal, approximate entropy, serial, and linear complexity, where their system passed all of them. It would have been a valuable source of information if any area where the proposal might fail had been mentioned, such as the size of the data and the data flow within it, which would have made the paper even more useful. Encryption, when done at the perception layer, helps the system by providing security from the ground level. But encryption is not done on the devices themselves. It does make sense that some devices might not be able to support this, but it was not clearly mentioned in the text and should have been tested for. Still, in all the context provided, this test was shown to pass and to work fluently.

Similarly, Guo et al. (2019) used SAFER in their paper, which mentioned that when a computer with very high computing capacity is used, the system was penetrated. In the real world, there are sectors where this cannot be used, as the data there is highly sensitive and there will be people looking for that data. Because of this reason, this system should introduce a double-checking mechanism so that penetration becomes harder. Additionally, Tuli et al. (2019) introduced FogBus, which uses a lightweight framework for their practical system. In this, they introduced the use of blockchain along with encryption, which provides a very high improvement in the performance of the network. To make it better, they used Wireless LAN, which is even more vulnerable because of its exposure to the general public and its susceptibility to interference from any source capable of interfering with the system.

Lastly, out of the many techniques that have been proposed, IoT-FBAC is one of the best proposed schemes, where Yan et al. (2019) proposed function-based access control, where access is only granted to users who have special privileges for those actions. These techniques, when implemented in blockchain, can provide a strong defence against hackers, as even if they gain access and act as a block, they will not be able to access the data, since they will not have sufficient privilege. And as blockchain is an indexed system, and all blocks should hold similar data to maintain integrity, it is highly difficult to obtain the data when encryption techniques like FBAC and FogBus are used in IoT.

6.4 Fail in technology

As researched by Li et al. (2019) in their research paper, there are many technologies being researched every day, but it takes special attention and dedication to develop the best possible technique. A technique like the LED framework was tested by the researchers, where they injected a fault and were successful in breaking the security barrier in a short interval of time. Similarly, every proposed technique requires similar attacks to be tested against, so that those systems can be tested vigorously and the best possible solution can be obtained.

7. Conclusion

From the first generation of computers to the current generation, providing security to the system has been a very important part of technology. Previously, people used to provide high security physically due to the expense of the system, whereas now people provide security to the data. Similarly, in the current technological evolution and the emerging Internet of Things technology, it is very important to provide the highest possible security.

Because of this reason, research is conducted in every corner of the world in the field of encryption, blockchain, and the Internet of Things, to come up with the best possible solution to make this technology secure. In the current scenario, data is one of the most important things. For this reason, providing high security to it becomes the most prominent factor. The Internet of Things is not just connected to one sector, like vehicles or industry, but it is expected to relate to every single

individual. It is expected to be connected from soil to humans. Thus, encryption is a very strong way by which data is secured.

Encryption can be implemented in many IoT devices and networks, but when it comes to highly constrained IoT devices, it will be almost impossible in many cases to introduce encryption directly to the IoT device. Some devices are designed to provide just an on and off signal in an IoT network. Some devices are so small that they can hardly fit anything except a radio antenna and a battery. In this situation, implementing security directly into the system will be very difficult to accomplish. For this reason, blockchain is the best possible solution when encryption is considered as well. Just like Bitcoin, blockchain can be used to implement encryption within it. When the identity of the device is not leaked, there will be less threat of data being stolen. The receiving blocks will be encrypted, which is the main connection of those devices with the main network. Thus, the data sent to the blockchain will only be accessible once it is received in the blocks where it is designed to be sent. In this block, encryption will be implemented before the data is transmitted to wherever it is required to be sent. Also, encryption techniques like AES and DES were researched as well, but these techniques are too large and highly energy-draining for small devices. Because of this reason, a technique like FogBus is recommended and proposed to be researched on a higher scale, so that if there are any faults that have not been identified by the authors, they can be pointed out — and the technique can either be considered unsuitable for use, or it can be considered one of the best solutions, with the help of other researchers.

Thus, FogBus, with the use of technologies like equality test, integrity test, and SAFER, should be used wherever possible. IoT should not just be limited to one technique for securing it, but techniques like AES, DES, SHA, and RSA, and methods like data sharing and publish-subscribe, should be used as appropriate for the designed network and the devices linked to it. If this is done, then low security can be expected for very low-threat devices, whereas when devices are at high risk, higher means of security can be provided, such as a dynamic security measure.

8. Future Work

The Internet of Things has come a long way since it was first used in the field of Information Technology. It has been growing with great success in terms of its acceptance in the modern world. Either knowingly or unknowingly, people are getting used to using IoT devices, whether it is the sensor in their car or the heat sensor at home. In the near future, encryption will be the protector of privacy and integrity when the Internet of Things has a blockchain-based network backbone, keeping it secure with various kinds of encryption techniques used specifically for specific devices.

FogBus, IoT-FBAC, and NDN technology can be further researched to produce better outputs in a blockchain-based IoT network. When these technologies are used together and fine-tuned, they can bring the near-possible future into the present.

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